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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Study of Displacement Damage Effects on Optocouplers with Proton Radiation (DIDOP II)</i>
Project TA identifier	TA10-336
General application	<i>Space and harsh environment</i>
Type of test	TNID
Group leader, Institute	<i>Yolanda Morilla, Centro Nacional de Aceleradores (CNA)</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>9th – 10th October, 2024</i>
Facility	PSI
Amount of access granted	8h

Objectives of the experiments

The Spanish National Accelerators Centre (Centro Nacional de Aceleradores) and the company ALTER Technology are leading a new study about radiation effects on optocouplers, with the technical support of principal optoelectronic manufactures, the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) and the European Space Agency (ESA).

In general, optoelectronic components are very radiation-sensitive devices. Despite this risk, optocouplers are essential components used to minimize noise and EMI by isolating noise between circuits and subsystems. Their use in space and harsh environments represents a challenge and therefore a clear motivation for this work. Although this family of devices has been studied over the years, new non-tested technologies are being more and more demanded.

The purpose of this project is to evaluate the main radiation effects on a representative set of optocouplers, selecting the more used and/or emerging components. The study will be accomplished in different blocks, with the following specific objectives:

- To characterize the Total Ionizing Dose (TID), Displacement Damage (DD), and Single Event Transients (SET) effects on the most relevant and/or more highly demanded optocouplers for the space industry and harsh environments.
- To explore synergistic effects and assess the applicability of the conventionally used Non-Ionizing Energy Loss (NIEL) scaling for these components.
- To include the test results in our database, PRECEDER, and analyze following our methodology to compare the new results with the corresponding archival data.

This campaign, corresponding to the RADNEXT TA10-336, is a continuation of our previous proton test campaign, packaging in the global project. We have focused here on the study of the degradation of the main electrical parameters of several sets of optocouplers using a monoenergetic proton beam, using

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different energies (60 MeV and 200 MeV).

Experiment test report

Complementing previous work on this type of device with protons, a new campaign was carried out. In this case, 12 part types were selected for testing that had not yet been tested with protons, but had previously been analyzed with neutrons. For each part type, a total of 5 samples were irradiated and one more was considered as a control reference.

The **Table I** shows the part types under test during this first neutron campaign, along with relevant information about manufacture, functionality, package, and the external view of each one.

Table I

DUT	Manufacture	Functionality	Package	External view
CSM128	ISOCOM	Low Input Current, Photodarlington Optocoupler	LCC-6	
CSM130	ISOCOM	Low Input Current, Photodarlington Optocoupler	LCC-6	
CSM131	ISOCOM	Transistor Output Optocoupler	LCC-6	
66224-105	MICROPAC	Transistor Output Optocoupler	LCC-6	
66212-300	MICROPAC	Transistor Output Optocoupler	LCC-4	
66266-303	MICROPAC	Transistor Output Optocoupler	LCC-6	

IBI110	ISOBAUD	Transistor Output Optocoupler	SMD-4	
OLC449	SKYWORK	Transistor Output Optocoupler	LCC-6	
IS49	ISOCOM	Transistor Output Optocoupler	LCC-6	
CSM1410	ISOCOM	Low Input Current, Photodarlington Optocoupler	LCC-6	
CSMV016	ISOCOM	Transistor Output Optocoupler	LCC-6	
66227-001	MICROPAC	Transistor Output Optocoupler	TO-05	

Below is a summary (**Table II**) of the date code, technology and electrical parameters measured during the test. The parameters were measured for each single device after each exposure step. All the DUTs were unbiased, that is, all the pins connected to ground. For each part type, a total of 5 samples were irradiated and one more was considered as a control. Two boards were manufactured ad-hoc to place the devices, adapting the configuration to the flux uniformity (Figure I). This is also useful to save time during the campaign, so that one board could be irradiated while the other devices were characterized.

Figure I

Table II

DUT	Date code	Technology	Electrical parameters
CSM128	2232	LED + Bipolar	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown current: IR (@VR=3V) Collector dark current: ICEO (@IF=0mA, VCE=20V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF1 (@IF=1.0mA, VCE=1V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF2 (@IF=3.0mA, VCE=1V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF1 (@IF=0.5mA, VCE=5V) Collector-Emitter saturation voltage: VCE(sat)(@IF=20mA, IC=5mA)
CSM130	2232	LED+ Hybrid	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown current: IR (@VR=3V) Collector- Emitter leakage current: ICEO (@IF=0mA, VCE=20V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF1 (@IF=1.0mA, VCE=1V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF2 (@IF=10mA, VCE=5V) Collector-Emitter saturation voltage: VCE(sat)(@IF=100mA, IC=150uA)
CSM131	2232	LED + Bipolar	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown current: IR (@VR=3V) Collector dark current: ICEO (@IF=0mA, VCE=20V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF1 (@IF=1.0mA, VCE=1V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF2 (@IF=10mA, VCE=5V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF1 (@IF=1.0mA, VCE=15V) Collector-Emitter saturation voltage: VCE(sat)(@IF=10mA, IC=15uA)

66224-105	2236	LED + Bipolar	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown current: IR (@VR=6V) Collector dark current: ICEO (@IF=0mA, VCE=20V) On-state collector current: ICE(ON) (@IF=1mA, VCE=20V) Current transfer ratio: CTR (--) Collector-Emitter saturation voltage: VCE(sat)(@IF=10mA, IC=15uA)
66212-300	2139B	GaAlAs LED + Bipolar	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown current: IR (@VR=2V) Collector dark current: ICEO (@IF=0mA, VCE=20V) On-state collector current: ICE(ON)1 (@IF=1mA, VCE=1V) On-state collector current: ICE(ON)2 (@IF=10mA, VCE=5V) Collector-Emitter saturation voltage: VCE(sat)(@IF=20mA, IC=10mA)
66266-303	1912	LED + Bipolar	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown current: IR (@VR=3V) Collector dark current: ICE(OFF) (@IF=0mA, VCE=20V) On-state collector current: ICE(ON) (@IF=1mA, VCE=5V) Current transfer ratio: CTR (@VCE=5V, IF=1mA) Collector-Emitter saturation voltage: VCE(sat)(@IF=2mA, IC=1mA)
IBI110	2050	AlGaAs LED + Bipolar	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown current: IR (@VR=3V) Collector dark current: ICEO (@IF=0mA, VCE=20V) Current transfer ratio: CTR1 (@VCE=5V, IF=1mA) Current transfer ratio: CTR2 (@VCE=5V, IF=10mA) Collector-Emitter saturation voltage: VCE(sat)(@IF=2mA, IC=1mA)
OLC449	--	LED + Bipolar	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown current: IR (@VR=2V) Collector to Emitter off-state leakage current: ICE(OFF) (@VCE=20V) Collector to Base off-state leakage current: ICB(OFF) (@VCE=20V) On-state collector to base current: ICB(ON)(@IF=1mA, VCE=5V) Collector-Emitter saturation voltage: VCE(sat)(@IF=1mA, IC=5mA)
IS49	2202	GaAs LED + Bipolar	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown current: IR (@VR=3V) Collector- Emitter leakage current: ICEO (@IF=0mA, VCE=20V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF1 (@IF=1.0mA, VCE=1V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF2 (@IF=3.0mA, VCE=1V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF3 (@IF=15.0mA, VCE=1V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF1 (@IF=10.0mA, VCE=5V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF4 (@IF=15mA, VCE=5V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF5 (@IF=1.0mA, VCE=15V) Collector-Emitter saturation voltage: VCE(sat)(@IF=20mA, IC=10 mA)
CSM1410	2235	GaAs LED + Bipolar	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=1.6mA) Reverse breakdown voltage: VR (@IR=10uA) Collector- Emitter leakage current: ICEO (@IF=0mA, VCE=20V) Logic Output current: IOH1 (@VCE=VBE=7V) Logic Output current: IOH2 (@VCE=VBE=18V) Logic Output voltage: VOL1 (@VCC=4.5, IF=1.0mA, IOL=10Ma) Logic High Supply current: ICCH (@IF=0mA, VCC=18V) Logic Low Supply current: ICCH (@IF=1.6mA, VCC=18V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF1 (@IF=1.0mA, VCE=1V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF2 (@IF=3.0mA, VCE=1V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF3 (@IF=15.0mA, VCE=1V)

CSMV016	2235	VCSEL LED + Bipolar	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown current: IR (@VR=3V) Collector- Emitter leakage current: ICEO (@IF=0mA, VCE=20V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF1 (@IF=1.0mA, VCE=1V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF2 (@IF=3.0mA, VCE=1V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF3 (@IF=15.0mA, VCE=1V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF1 (@IF=10.0mA, VCE=5V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF4 (@IF=15mA, VCE=5V) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF5 (@IF=1.0mA, VCE=15V) Collector-Emitter saturation voltage: VCE(sat)(@IF=20mA, IC=10 mA)
66227-001	M2240	GaAlAs LED + Bipolar	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown current: IR (@VR=2V) Collector dark current: ICE(OFF) (@IF=0mA, VCE=20V) On-state collector current: ICE(ON) (@IF=1mA, VCE=5V) Current transfer ratio: CTR (@VCE=5V, IF=1mA) Collector-Emitter saturation voltage: VCE(sat)(@IF=2mA, IC=2mA)

In the **Table III**, the dosimetry details are presented, as provided by the PSI staff.

Table III

Energy (MeV)	Board	Flux (p/cm ² s)	Fluence (p/cm ²)			
			Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step4
200	#01	3.52E+08	1,00E+11	5,00E+11	1,00E+12	--
200	#02	3.50E+08	1,00E+11	5,00E+11	--	--

All the devices have shown degradation when exposed to proton radiation, as expected. However, there are devices that show a higher tolerance to radiation and therefore exhibit lower degradation. More details and the proper study of the data will be published, when the full analysis is completed, in different journal publications and/or conferences (NSREC 2025, RADECS 2025 and IEEE editorials).

The figure below (**Figure II**) shows an example of how the same parameter, measured for two different part types of devices at the same energy (200 MeV).

Figure II

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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